

No	Jobcard	Worktype	Manhours
1	Pre Dock Engine Run Up	OPC	5
2	A/C Receiving & Inventory	ISP	5
3	Unload replacement center Ing	REM	20
4	Aircraft Symmetry / Aircraft <i>Alignment</i> Check	CHK	17
5	Leveling and Shoring Aircraft - Jack and Trestle	CHK	2
6	Remove Engine #1	REM	55
7	Remove Engine #2	REM	55
8	Remove Engine #3	REM	55
9	Remove Engine #4	REM	55
10	Remove Propeller #1	REM	55
11	Remove Propeller #2	REM	55
12	Remove Propeller #3	REM	55
13	Remove Propeller #4	REM	55
14	Preservation of Engine #1	SVC	65
15	Preservation of Engine #2	SVC	65
16	Preservation of Engine #3	SVC	65
17	Preservation of Engine #4	SVC	65
18	Preservation of Propeller #1	SVC	24
19	Preservation of Propeller #2	SVC	24
20	Preservation of Propeller #3	SVC	24
21	Preservation of Propeller #4	SVC	24
22	Removal Of External Wire Antena HF #1 & HF# 2	REM	5
23	APU Preservation	SVC	6
24	Removal A/C battery	REM	2
25	Remove LH Wheel Well Access Panels	REM	7
26	Remove LH MLG Brake & Wheel	REM	17
27	Remove LH MLG Struts	REM	48

28	Remove RH Wheel Well Access Panels	REM	7
29	Remove RH MLG Brake & Wheel	REM	17
30	Remove RH MLG Struts	REM	48
31	Remove LH Out board Wing Flap and Flap Carriages	REM	18
32	Remove LH Center Wing Flaps Torque Shaft	REM	18
33	Removal LH Fillet-Uner Wing Panel And Fairing	REM	5
34	Removal RH Fillet-Uner Wing Panel And Fairing	REM	5
35	Remove RH Out board Wing Flap and Flap Carriages	REM	18
36	Remove RH Center Wing Flaps Torque Shaft	REM	18
37	Remove Flap Drive Control Assembly	REM	9
38	Remove LH Ailerons	REM	17
39	Remove RH Ailerons	REM	17
40	Remove LH Aux Tank Bladder tank	REM	129
41	Remove RH Aux Tank Bladder tank	REM	129
42	Remove LH External Tanks and Pylons	REM	51
43	Remove RH External Tanks and Pylons	REM	51
44	Remove <i>Center Wing Box</i> LH Leading Edges	REM	65
45	Remove <i>Center Wing Box</i> Required LH Panels And Fairings	REM	45
46	Remove <i>Center Wing Box</i> Required LH Dry Bay Access Doors	REM	16
47	Remove <i>Center Wing Box</i> Required RH Leading Edges	REM	16
48	Remove <i>Center Wing Box</i> Required RH Panels And Fairings	REM	11
49	Remove <i>Center Wing Box</i> Required RH Dry Bay Access Doors	REM	16
50	Removed Survival kits (life raft)from Existing Center Wing	REM	6

51	Removed Fuel plumbing System from Existing Center Wing	REM	31
52	Remove LH Outer Wings	REM	46
53	Remove RH Outer Wings	REM	46
54	Remove Floor Panel FS 517 - FS 597	REM	46
55	Remove Duct Bleed Air System & Insulation Blankets	REM	41
56	Remove Aircond System & Insulation Blankets	REM	44
57	Remove All Required Hydraulic Systems	REM	21
58	Disconnect and Stow All Harnesses	REM	36
59	Disconnect and Stow Engine control Cable	REM	6
60	Disconnect and Stow Aileron Control Cable	REM	6
61	Disconnect and Stow Rudder Control Cable	REM	6
62	Disconnect and Stow Elevator Control cable	REM	6
63	Disconnect and Stow Flap control Cable Aft	REM	6
64	Remove and Retain All Harnesses from Existing Center Wing	REM	20
65	Remove Center Wing Trailing Edges, Fwd and Aft Fairings from Existing Center Wing	REM	65
66	Removed Fwd Pressure Panels	REM	2
67	Removed Aft Pressure Panels	REM	2
68	Replace LH FS597 MLG Vertical Beam Track	RAR	20
69	Replace RH FS597 MLG Vertical Beam Track	RAR	20
70	Replace LH FS517 MLG Vertical Beam Track	RAR	5
71	Replace RH FS517 MLG Vertical Beam Track	RAR	20
72	Replace RH FS528 MLG Vertical Beam Track	RAR	20
73	Replace LH FS528 MLG Vertical Beam Track (include attaching Part)	RAR	20
74	Replace RH FS577 MLG Vertical Beam Track (include attaching Part)	RAR	20

75	Replace LH FS577 MLG Vertical Beam Track (include attaching Part)	RAR	20
76	Replace RH FS588 MLG Vertical Beam Track (include attaching Part)	RAR	20
77	Replace LH FS588 MLG Vertical Beam Track (include attaching Part)	RAR	20
78	Replace RH FS 497 upper bow beam And	RAR	10
79	Replace LH FS497 upper bow beam And	RAR	222
80	Replace RH FS 537 upper bow beam And	RAR	251
81	Replace LH FS537 upper bow beam end	RAR	5
82	Replace RH FS 557 upper bow beam end	RAR	20
83	Replace LH FS 557 upper bow beam end	RAR	5
84	Replace Fwd LH BL20 Longerons Splices	RAR	10
85	Replace Fwd RH BL20 Longerons Splices	RAR	10
86	Replace Aft LH BL20 Longerons Splices	RAR	10
87	Replace Aft RH BL20 Longerons Splices	RAR	10
88	Remove all fastener from RH Attach Angle Assy to <i>Center Wing Box</i>	REM	193
89	Remove all fastener from LH Attach Angle Assy to <i>Center Wing Box</i>	REM	193
90	Center wing Quick Fix an Engineering disposition Removal Center Wing Box	REM	2
91	Remove Existing Center Wing	REM	100
92	Replaced LH Wing Attach Angle Center Wing To Fuselage, BL 61625, FS 477-617	REM	499
93	Replaced RH Wing Attach Angle Center Wing To Fuselage, BL 61625, FS 477-617	REM	499
94	Center wing Quick Fix an Engineering disposition installation of New Wing	DVI	1
95	Install New Center Wing	INS	30
96	Install LH Longeron Splice Bar, BL61 FS 477 lower	INS	5

97	Install RH Longeron Splice Bar, BL61 FS 477 lower	INS	5
98	Install LH Longeron Splice Bar, BL61 FS 477 Upper	INS	5
99	Install RH Longeron Splice Bar, BL61 FS 477 Upper	INS	5
100	Install LH Longeron Splice Bar, BL61 FS 617 lower	INS	5
101	Install RH Longeron Splice Bar, BL61 FS 617 lower	INS	5
102	Install LH Longeron Splice Bar, BL61 FS 617 Upper	INS </td <td>5</td>	5
103	Install RH Longeron Splice Bar, BL61 FS 617 Upper	INS	5
104	Install LH Sidewall Skin Instl	INS	3
105	Install RH Sidewall Skin Instl	INS	3

Dimensions
Head size: 311(W) x 556(H) mm
Head weight: 17.7kg (19.5kg w/IFM option)
Controller size: 282(L) x 158(D) x 214(H) mm
Controller weight: 5.2kg

Range
Horizontal envelope: +/- 270°
Vertical envelope: +75° to -50°
Minimum working range: 0 meters
Maximum working range: 55m with select targets
40m with standard 1.5" & 7/8" SMRs
30m with standard 1/2" SMR

Environmental
Altitude: -700 to 2,450 meters
Humidity: 0 to 95% non-condensing
Operating Temperature: -15°C to 50°C

Laser Emission**
633-635 nm Laser, 1 milliwatt max/cw.
Class II Laser Product

Distance Measurement Performance***

Agile ADM Resolution: 0.5µm Sample rate: 10,000/sec Accuracy: 8µm + 0.4µm/m R0 Parameter: 8µm	Optional Interferometer Resolution: 0.158µm Accuracy: 2µm + 0.4µm/m Maxim. radial velocity: 4m/sec R0 Parameter: 8µm
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Angle Measurement Performance**
Angular accuracy: 10µm + 2.5µm/m
Maximum angular velocity: 180°/sec
Precision Level Accuracy: +/- 2 arcseconds

Point-to-Point Typical Accuracy***

Horizontal Scale Bar Measurement (2.3 m)			In-Line Distance Measurement			
Range (m)	ADM (mm)	IFM (mm)	Length (m)	Distance (m)	ADM (mm)	IFM (mm)
2	0.022	0.021	2 - 5	3	0.009	0.003
5	0.032	0.032	2 - 10	8	0.011	0.005
10	0.049	0.049	2 - 20	18	0.015	0.009
20	0.085	0.085	2 - 30	28	0.019	0.013
30	0.120	0.120	2 - 40	38	0.023	0.017
40	0.156	0.156	2 - 50*	48	0.027	0.021
50*	0.191	0.191	2 - 55*	53	0.029	0.023
55*	0.209	0.209				

**With selected targets.

**Product complies with radiation performance standards under the food, drug, and cosmetics act and international standard IEC 60825-1 2001-08.

***Typical Accuracy shown is half the Maximum Permissible Error (MPE) and variation in air temperature is not included. MPE and all accuracy specifications are calculated per ASME B89.4.19 - 2006 Standard.

Specifications, descriptions, and technical data may be subject to change. Protected by U.S. patents: 7327446, 7352446, 7486401

